

MORPHOFUNCTIONAL CHANGES OF RAT ADRENAL GLANDS UNDER THE INFLUENCE OF ENERGY DRINKS

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ABSTRACT

The adrenal glands are considered the main endocrine organs responsible for the body's stress response. The safety profile of energy drinks, particularly their long-term effects, has not been sufficiently studied from a morphological perspective. Therefore, this study was aimed at scientifically evaluating the effects of energy drinks on the adrenal glands.

Introduction: The adrenal glands are considered the main endocrine organs responsible for the body's stress response. The safety profile of energy drinks, particularly their long-term effects, has not been sufficiently studied from a morphological perspective. Therefore, this study was aimed at scientifically evaluating the effects of energy drinks on the adrenal glands.

Objective: To identify morphological changes in adrenal gland tissues in rats exposed to energy drinks.

Materials and Methods: The study involved 60 outbred male rats, divided into two groups:

- **Experimental group (n=40):** received energy drinks at doses of 2 and 4 ml/kg.
- **Control group (n=20):** intact rats without intervention.

The energy drink was administered daily at 09:00 via intragastric gavage. The rats were sacrificed at intervals ranging from 1 to 7 hours after administration. Histological analysis and serum cortisol levels were evaluated. Student's t-test was used for statistical analysis.

Results: Exposure to energy drinks led to the following changes in the adrenal glands:

- Enlargement of the reticular zone and increased cell size;
- Proliferation of lipid-rich, light cytoplasm cells in the zona glomerulosa;
- A 3.6–4-fold increase in serum cortisol levels.

Conclusion: Long-term exposure to energy drinks enhances adrenal gland activity in rats and intensifies the endocrine stress response. These findings indicate significant alterations in the body's homeostasis and adaptive

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